

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS.

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From a historical point of view, the development of the system of international legal regulation of the protection of human rights has certain patterns. The key stages in its formation were the development of the theory of natural law, the participation of citizens in government, the possibility of holding officials accountable, guarantees of personal integrity, freedom of speech and elections, the right to appeal, and the doctrine of separation of powers.

The issue of protecting human rights has always been relevant, but it was in the second half of the 19th century that awareness of transnationality of this problem went beyond domestic issues and attracted the attention of the international community. Approaches that recognize the priority of rights and freedoms in relations between the individual and the state were important for the development of the system of human rights protection. Individual freedom, including freedom from government interference in personal interests, has become crucial. At the same time, the state guaranteed the protection of the rights and freedoms of its citizens. The principles of freedom and equality preceded the idea of human rights. Friedrich Engels noted that it took millennia to realize equality as the basis of equal rights in the state, which began to be perceived as natural. A significant role was played by the doctrine of natural human rights, which are innate and do not depend on the historical period or decisions of the state, emphasizing the autonomy of the individual.

Thus, an analysis of the key stages in the development of teachings on the protection of human rights shows that mere awareness of the need for such a category was not enough; The formation of the system occurred as organizations were created whose purpose was to protect human rights. Since 1945, the international community began to actively develop and approve international standards in the field of human rights¹. The most important documents were the Charter of the United Nations (1945)² and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)³. The main role of the UN is to take a responsible approach to

¹ file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/S_2006_945-RU.pdf

² <https://www.un.org/ru/about-us/un-charter>

³ Vseobshchaya deklaraciya prav cheloveka. Prinyata rezolyuciej 217 A (III) General'noj Assamblei OON 10 dekabrya 1948 goda. Sobranie zakonod- atel'stva RF, 1998 №2.

global issues, find solutions and establish a balance through the joint efforts of governments to solve pressing problems.

The question of the regulatory role of the UN and its Charter is the subject of both theoretical and practical research. This issue is of a significant integral nature for the formation of a new world order. The UN Charter, by its nature and structure, is multifaceted. It includes provisions related to various spheres of life and law: humanitarian, political, military, economic, environmental and others, which makes it a classic model for states. The UN Charter is rightly recognized as one of the first multilateral treaties in the history of international relations. Its adoption laid the foundation for cooperation between states in the difficult task of promoting and respecting human rights and freedoms.

It is important to note that the Charter is also versatile in its tasks. The promotion, activation and development of human rights is not its only goal; The Charter is also aimed at harmoniously and coherently obliging states to be committed to the development of international cooperation in various fields. Activities carried out by the UN are directly or indirectly aimed at implementing one of the central objectives defined in the Charter, namely promoting and protecting human rights.

The UN Charter, given its legal nature, does not refer to an exhaustive list of fundamental rights and freedoms guaranteed to a person. However, it is one of the first international documents that determined the need for a universal approach to ensuring individual rights. It enshrines the globally universal principle of respect for rights and freedoms without discrimination of any kind.

The Preamble calls for the UN's determination to strengthen faith in human rights, the dignity and worth of the human person. The first document in international relations that defined a list of fundamental human rights and freedoms was the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 10, 1948. The Declaration acts as a task that states and peoples strive to achieve. It serves as a measure to determine the level of respect and compliance with international human rights instruments.

The protection of human rights is one of the main goals of a developed democratic state governed by the rule of law⁴. In the process of its development and formation, such a state comes to the fair conclusion that it is man who is the creator of history. In order for the state not to stop developing, it is necessary that a person, realizing his rights and freedoms, become an individual capable of directing the state on the path of progress.

⁴ <https://www.un.org/ru/our-work/protect-human-rights>

In the modern world, the state of the economy, the problems of the functioning of socio-political institutions and the legal culture of the majority of the population of Uzbekistan are influenced by crisis phenomena⁵. In this regard, the state of affairs in the field of observance of human and civil rights and freedoms is also far from satisfactory. Various aspects of observance of human and civil rights and freedoms (personal, political, socio-economic and cultural) do not go unnoticed by both ordinary citizens and representatives of the government apparatus and human rights defenders.

By ratifying international human rights treaties, governments undertake the responsibility to take various measures at the domestic level and create appropriate legislative frameworks that are compatible with treaty obligations. The national legal system is designed to provide normative protection of human rights defined and guaranteed by international law. When national judicial proceedings are ineffective in addressing human rights violations, mechanisms and procedures exist at the regional and international levels for individual and group complaints that can ensure compliance with international human rights standards at various levels.

In international law, every person has the right to protection, regardless of his affiliation with any state. International law guarantees rights and freedoms to a person, without requiring the implementation of specific responsibilities in return. It focuses on the fact that a person has rights, enjoys them and realizes them without the intervention of any state, even the one of which he is a citizen. This demonstrates the universality of human rights. Considering the category of “rights and freedoms” as the possibility of certain behavior at some stage of human development, it becomes clear that in order to recognize and protect human rights it is necessary to go beyond the domestic level. However, for a real opportunity to freely enjoy rights, it is necessary that they are reflected and enshrined in regulations.

The concept of “citizen's rights” is significantly narrower in terms of the scope of the aspects involved. This is explained by the fact that the state, for objective reasons, seeks to bind itself in a legal sense with its citizens, that is, with people who constantly “belong” to this state and, no less important, bear constitutional and other responsibilities. This is permitted in international law, in particular through a document such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of December 16, 1966⁶.

⁵ https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-08/ECE.CEP_.188.Rus_.pdf

⁶ https://www.un.org/ru/documents/decl_conv/conventions/pactpol.shtml

Many modern states recognize human rights as the highest value. Therefore, it is inherent in countries and government bodies to realize that human rights are, in a sense, a supranational category. To protect their rights, a person can turn to both the government authorities of his country and international organizations.

Human rights precede the exercise of certain freedoms and provide the opportunity to independently choose the way of behavior. These rights themselves allow a person to ensure their protection; they serve as conditions and means for this, for example, the right to a fair trial.

The right to protection follows and accompanies the implementation of subjective rights. However, this cannot be effectively implemented without the active participation of the state, and in some cases, without its leading and guiding role in organizing this protection. Protection of rights is understood in various aspects. First, these are “preliminary measures” aimed at eliminating obstacles or contradictions on the way to the effective, reasonable and fair implementation of the law. Secondly, these are measures of a subsequent nature, applied after the fact, that is, relating to the restoration of an already violated right, elimination of violations, punishment of violators and prevention of new violations. All these elements are interconnected. Therefore, the protection of human rights in international law is systematic.

The substantive element of the system of international legal regulation of the protection of human rights are principles. The principles are enshrined in regulations at various levels, including declarative and constitutional acts. They reflect such essential principles as fairness and respect.

Certain principles are closely related to the legal status of the individual; this connection reflects the relationship between the state and the individual. This is confirmed by the Convention for the Protection of Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted in Rome in 1950. In particular, it includes provisions on such principles as respect, implementation, recognition and protection of human rights and freedoms, taking into account the principle of the legal status of the individual.

The principles of their protection follow from the classification of fundamental rights and freedoms. For some of them there are specific forms of protection. For example, the principle of unconditionality applies to such rights and freedoms as personal ones. That is, the state cannot refer to the lack of necessary mechanisms for their successful implementation. At the same time, rights such as economic ones are closely related to the capabilities of the state,

including its material resources at a certain stage of historical, in particular economic, development. However, this group of rights must also be enforced in good faith and to the maximum extent possible. An analysis of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 leads to such conclusions.

One of the main principles is the unity of rights and responsibilities, which includes the responsibilities of both the owner of the rights and other subjects regarding the observance of rights, as well as the principle of equality of rights and freedoms, based on non-discrimination in their use, is reflected in legal acts at various levels. In particular, at the domestic level this is most often enshrined in the Constitution of the state.

Considering such an element of the system for regulating the protection of human rights as a form, it becomes obvious that this is, to some extent, a process representing a range of measures and procedures of a certain nature aimed at implementation by law enforcement agencies, including direct human participation, law enforcement actions and measures to protect rights and restoration of violated rights. The forms of protection are varied, and their choice may be determined by a number of factors, including the nature of the claims that are the object of protection, the set of legal and factual conditions under which the right was violated, as well as the real capabilities of a person to protect the right.

A special role in ensuring the right to judicial protection is given to constitutional guarantees, through which the restoration of violated rights is possible. The constitutional right to appeal, or file a complaint, is one of the fundamental and inalienable human rights in the system. Rights often come with responsibilities. In this case, the constitutional right to file a complaint is accompanied by the obligation of state bodies and local governments to accept and consider complaints, as well as make informed decisions and respond to applicants.

Restrictions on rights are exceptional, established in a constitutional and legal manner and have a legal basis and clear goals. These purposes, according to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, include ensuring due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others, and meeting the just demands of morality and welfare in a democratic society. The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms significantly expands these goals, including maintaining state and public security, preventing

disorder and crime, protecting health and morals, protecting the reputation of citizens and others.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the regulation of restrictions on rights and freedoms is based on the constancy, steadfastness and inviolability of these rights. The law cannot unreasonably diminish rights and freedoms. The state introduces restrictions only if there are justified reasons, such as protecting the foundations of the constitutional order, ensuring the defense and security of the country. These restrictions can only be established on the basis of law and to the extent necessary and reasonable.

Human rights today are presented as an expression by states of historically established freedoms. The development of society and the state at various stages should not only encourage, but also promote human rights. The emergence of ideas of democracy, the rule of law and civil society contributed to the emergence of the concepts of human rights.

The development of society and the state, as well as such integral elements of democracy as the rule of law, civil society and a high legal culture, is closely related to the effective implementation of human rights and freedoms.

In conclusion, the establishment and development of a system of international human rights protection is a process that requires constant attention and effort. Only through cooperation, mutual respect and continuous work can peace, justice and equality be achieved for every person on the planet.

